

REVIEW ARTICLE ON NASYA KARMA

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ABSTRACT

The process of instillation of medicines through nasal cavity is known as *Nasya Karma*. It is the unique process of *Shodhana Chikitsa* in which medicines reach to the brain and eject the vitiated *Dosha* responsible for producing the diseases. Every *Shodhana* procedure of *Panchakarma* is simple, easy and very much beneficial if done with its proper & complete knowledge. Complications (*Vyapada*) may be arise if not go through proper method as mentioned in scripts. *Nasya Karma* is one of the important *Panchakarma* it is short, but complicated procedure if not go through proper way. Similarly knowledge of patient regarding *Nasya Arha-Anarha* is essential. So *Panchakarma* physician should have to know each and everything about *Nasya* if he wants proper benefit of *Nasya*.

KEYWORDS: *Nasya, Shodhana Chikitsa, Nasya Vyapada, Nasya Arha-Anarha.***INTRODUCTION**

The *Nasya Karma* is a therapeutic measure where the medicated oil, decoction and powder etc. are administered through nose to eliminate the vitiated humors in head for the treatment of ear, nose, throat and neurological diseases. In *Ayurvedic* texts, *Acharya Charaka* has used the term “*Nastah Pracchardana*”. Which denotes *Shodhana* done by *Nasya*. As stated by *Acharya Sushruta* the medicines are administered through the nose is known as *Nasya*. *Nasa Dhatu* is used in sense of nose (*Nasa Nasikayam*).

Nose is considered as a gateway of *Shirah*. The drugs administered through *Nasya* reach to brain and eliminate morbid *Doshas* responsible for producing diseases.^[1] *Nasya* is the only *Shodhana* therapy which directly influences *Indriyas*.

औषधमौषधसिद्धोवास्नेहोनसिकभ्यांदीयतजतिनस्यम्॥ (सु. चि. ४०/२१)

As said by *Acharya Sushruta* administration of medicine or medicated oils through nostril is called as *Nasya*.^[2]

REVIEW OF LITERATURE**Etymology of word *Nasya***

The word *Nasya* is derived from *NASA Dhatu*. It means *GATI*; meaning movement towards the internal structure mainly to head through the nose, accessory structure of nose. *NASA Dhatu* is used in sense of nose. (*Vachaspatyam*) The literal meaning of the word *Nasya* is, being in the nose or the things beneficial to the nose.

Synonyms of *Nasya*

- *Shirovirechana, Shirovireka, Murdhavirechana*^[3]
- *Nasta Pracchardana*^[4]
- *Nasta Karma, Navana*,^[5]

Definition of Nasya

- The procedure by which medicaments or medicated Ghee & oils are administered through nose (nostrils) is called as Nasya.^[6]

- Nasya karma is a therapeutic measure in which the drug is administered through nose that eliminates vitiated Doshas situated in head and helps in clearing the disease.^[7]

Table No. 1: Classification of Nasya.

No.	Acharyas	No.	Classification	Reference
1	Charaka	3	According to mode of action- <i>Rechana, Tarpana, Shamana</i>	<i>Ca.Si.9/92</i>
		5	According to the method of administration- <i>Navana, Avapida, Dhamapana, Dhuma, Pratimarsha</i>	<i>Ca.Si.9/89</i>
		7	According to various parts of drugs utilized – <i>Phala, Patra, Mula, Kanda, Pushpa, Niriyasa, Tvak</i>	<i>Ca.Vi.8/151</i>
2	<i>Susruta</i>	5	<i>Shirovirechana, Pradhmana, Avapida, Nasya, Patimarsha</i>	<i>Su.Ci.40/21</i>
3	<i>Vagbhata</i>	3	<i>Virechana, Brimhana, Shamana</i>	<i>A.H.Su.20/2</i>
4	<i>Kasyapa</i>	2	<i>Brimhana, Karshana</i>	<i>Ka.Si.2 & 4</i>
5	<i>Sarangadhara</i>	2	<i>Rechana, Snehana</i>	<i>Sa.Ut.8/2,11,24</i>
6	<i>Bhoja</i>	2	<i>Prayogika, Snaihika</i>	<i>Dalhana Su.Ci.40/31</i>
7	<i>Videha</i>	2	<i>Sanjna Prabodhaka, Stambhana</i>	

A. Description of types of Nasya Karma On the basis of its mode of action^[8]

1. Rechana-The *Rechana Nasya* denotes elimination of vitiated Doshas from *Urdhvajatrugata* (above clavicle part of body). *Churna* or *Sneha* prepared from required drugs which is to be used for *Shirovirechana*. Like *Apamarga, Pippali, Maricha* etc. It can also be given with *Tikshana Sneha Kwatha* or *Swarasa* of *Shirovirechana* drugs or by dissolving these drugs in *Madya, Madhu, Saindhava, Aasava* etc.^[9]

2. Tarpana- *Sneha* prepared with *Vata-Pittahara Dravya* and the *Dravyas of Madhura Skanda* should be used.^[10] According to *Vagbhata Sneha* prepared with *Snigdha* and *Madhura* Drugs or with the drugs described useful for that particular diseases should be used.^[11]

3. Shamana Nasya- as the name indicates, *Shamana Nasya* used for elevation of Doshas situated in *Shira*

Pradesha (head region). The *Sneha* prepared with suitable palliative drugs may use for *Shamana Nasya*.^[12]

According to method of administration

NAVANA NASYA

Navana is one of the important and well applicable therapies of *Nasya Karma*. It can be mainly classified into *Snehana* and *Shodhana*. *Navana* is administered by instilling the drops of a medicated oil or *Ghrta* in the nose.^[13]

A) SNEHANA NASYA

It gives strength to all the *Dhatu* and is used as *Dhatuposhaka*.

Drug

Sarpi, Taila, Vasa and *Majja* processed either singly and in combination with appropriate drugs. Generally, *Sneha* should be processed in *Vata Pittahara Dravyas*.

Dosage schedule for Sneha Nasya**Table No. 2: According to Acharya Sushruta.**

Type of dose	Dose
Hina Matra	8 drops in each nostril (In total 16 Bindus).
Madhyama matra	<i>Sukti Pramana</i> (In total 32 Bindus)- 16 drops in each nostril
Uttama Matra	<i>Panisukti Pramana</i> (In total 64 Bindus)- 32 drops in each nostril

Types – According to *Vagbhata, Sneha Nasya* is further classified into 2 types based on dose.

i) *Marsha* ii) *Pratimarsha*

B) Shodhana

Shirovirechana, which is mentioned by *Sushruta*, can be categorized in *Shodhana* type of *Navana Nasya*. In this type of *Nasya*, oil prepared by *Shirovirechana Dravyas* like *Pippali, Shigru* etc. can be used.

Dose**Table No. 4: According to Sushruta (Su.Chi.40/36).**

Type of dose	Dose
<i>Uttama</i>	8 drops
<i>Madhyama</i>	6 drops
<i>Hina</i>	4 drops.

AVAPIDA NASYA

It is a type of *Shodhana Nasya*. The word *Avapida Nasya* means *Nasya* given by extracted juice of leaves or pest (*Kalk*) of required medicine.^[14]

Types

It is mainly of two types.

Stambhana Nasya

Shodhana Nasya.

Chakrapani has mentioned three types

1) *Shodhana* 2) *Stambhana* 3) *Shamana*

Videha has mentioned two types

1) *Sadnya Prabodhana* 2) *Stambhana*

Drugs

For *Shodhana* purpose *Kalka* of *Tikshna dravyas* like *Saindhava*, *Pippali* etc. have been mentioned as *Avapida Nasya* and for *Stambhana* purpose *Stambhana* drugs have been described.

Dose

Table No. 5.

<i>Hina Matra</i>	4 drops
<i>Madhyama Matra</i>	6 drops
<i>Uttama Matra</i>	8 drops

Dhmapana Nasya

Here according to reference stated the fine powder of drugs is blown into the nostrils with the help of *Naadi Yantra*, which is six *Anguli* in length. The fine powder of drugs is taken at one end and air is blown from the other end, so that the medicine enters into the nostrils.

Dhoom Nasya- Medicines used in the form of smoke & inhaled through nose to remove *Kapha* situated in oral cavity, throat, and exhaled through mouth. Inhalation of *Dhoom* i.e. medicated smoke. A) *Prayogika* B) *Snaihika* C) *Vairechanika*,^[15] are subtypes of *Dhoom Nasya* Acharya *Sushruta* had not described it as a type of *Nasya*.

MARSHA NASYA

According to *Vagbhata* 6, 8, 10 drops of *Sneha* is instilled to each nostril this is known as *Marsha*. That it gives quick result and more effective than *Pratimarsha Nasya* but *Marsha Nasya* gives more side effects (*Vyapada*).

Dose

Table No. 6: According to *Vagbhata*.

<i>Hina Matra</i>	6 Bindu in each nostril.
<i>Madhyama Matra</i>	8 Bindu in each nostril.
<i>Uttama Matra</i>	10 Bindu in each nostril

Table No. 7: According to *Sharangadhara*.

<i>Hina Matra</i>	1 Shaana (8 Bindu)
<i>Madhyama Matra</i>	4 Shaana (32 Bindu)
<i>Uttama Matra</i>	8 Shaana (64 Bindu)

Pratimarsha Nasya- *Nasya* which can be given daily at any stage without any pre planning without any post procedure caution too is termed as *Pratimarsha Nasya* in

this type of *Nasya* generally different *Sneha* (oleaginous substances) are used sub, there is no any classification of *Pratimarsha Nasya*.

Dose

Two drops morning and two drops evening.

Classification of Nasya Karma On the basis of various parts of drugs used in it^[16]

1. *Phala*- e.g. *Pippali*, *Maricha*, *Vidanga*.
2. *Patra*- e.g.-*Surasa*, *Kutheraka*, *Gandira*.
3. *Mula*- e.g. *Vacha*, *Apamarga*, *Shweta*, *Jyotishmati*.
4. *Kanda*- e.g. *Haridra*, *Shrungabera*, *Mulaka*, *Lashuna*
5. *Pushpa*-e.g. *Lodhra*, *Madanphala*, *Saptarna*.
6. *Niryasa*- e.g. *Devdaru*, *Sarala*, *Agru*.
7. *Twaka* e.g. *Tejovati*, *Varaha*, *Engudi*, *Shigru*.

B. Classification of Nasya Karma according to Acharya Sushruta^[17]

तद् द्विविधम्- शिरोविरेचनस्नेहनञ्च । तद् द्विविधमपिपञ्चधा।

तद्यथा – नस्यं शिरोविरेचनं प्रतिमर्शः अवपिद प्रधमनं च

तेषुनस्यंप्रधानंशिरोविरेचनञ्च नस्यविकल्पः प्रतिमर्शः

शिरोविरेचनविकल्पावपिडः प्रधमनं चः

नस्यशब्दःपञ्चधनियमितः। (सु.चि. ४०/२१)

Nasya Karma is broadly divided into two types A) *Shirovirechana* B) *Snehana*, and Further divided into 5 types on the basis of methodology.

1. *Nasya*. 2. *Shirovirechana* 3. *Pratimarsha* 4. *Avapida* 5. *Pradhamana*.

C. Classification of Nasya Karma according to Vagbhatacharya (Ashtanga Samgraha & Hridaya) Classification of Nasya Karma on the basis of Functions^[18,19]

1. **Virechana-** It is *Shodhana* type of *Nasya* in which *Kwatha* and *Swarasa* of *Tikshana* drugs, *Madhu*, *Asava* or *Sneha* processed by appropriate drugs are used. Medicines used for *Vairechanika Nasya* are *Apamarga*, *Pippali*, *Maricha*,^[20] Indicated in *Urdhvajatrugta Vikara*, *Gauravta*, *Shofa*, *Upadeha*, *Kandu*, *Stambha*, *Abhishyada*, *Paka*, *Vairasya*, *Arochaka*, *Swarabheda*, *Krimi*, *Pratishayaya*, *Apasamara*, etc.^[21]

Table No. 7: General Indications of *Nasya*.

Sr.no	Nasya Yogya	Charak (Ch.Si 2/22)	Sushr ut (chi.40/23)	Sangrah a (Su.29/6)	Hridaya (Su.16/24)
1.	<i>Shirastambha</i> (stiffness of head),	+	+	-	-
2.	<i>Manyastambha</i> (stiffness of neck),	+	-	-	-
3.	<i>Dantastambha</i> (stiffness of tooth),	+	-	-	-
4.	<i>Galagraha</i> (Tightness in throat),	+	-	-	-
5.	<i>Hanugraha</i> (Tightness mandible), In	+	-	-	-
6.	<i>Pinasa</i> (Running nose),	+	+	+	+
7.	<i>Galashundika, Timiar</i> (blindness),	+	-	+	-
8.	<i>Vartamaroga</i> (Disease eyelids), Of	+	-	-	-
9.	<i>Vyanga</i> (Moles),	+	-	-	-
10.	<i>Upjivhika</i>	+	-	-	-
11.	<i>Ardhavabhedaka</i> (Migraine),	+	+	-	-
12.	<i>Skandarog</i> (Disease of shoulder),	+	-	+	-
13.	<i>Ansashoola</i> (Pain in Scapular region)	+	-	-	-
14.	<i>Nasikaroga</i> (Disease of nose),	+	-	-	-
15.	<i>Karna Roga</i> (Ear Diseases),	+	-	-	-
16.	<i>Akshiroga</i> (ophthalmic diseases),	+	-	+	+
17.	<i>Murdharoga, Shiroroga</i> (Head diseases),	+	+	+	+
18.	<i>Ardita</i> (Bell's palsy),	+	-	+	+
19.	<i>Aptanaka</i> (Tetanus),	+	+	+	-
20.	<i>Galganda</i> (Goitere),	+	-	+	+
21.	<i>Dantashoola</i> (Toothache),	+	-	+	+
22.	<i>Dantaharsha</i>	+	-	-	-
23.	<i>Dantachala</i>	+	-	-	-
24.	<i>Akshiraji, Arbuda</i> (cancer),	+	-	-	+
25.	<i>Shleshmaabhivyapta Talu, Kantha, Shira</i> (Deposition of <i>Kapha</i> in palate, throat, head)	-		+	+
26.	<i>Arachoka</i>	-	+	+	+
27.	<i>Krimi</i> (Worms in supraclavicular region)	-	+	+	+
28.	<i>Pratishyaya</i>	-	+	+	+
29.	<i>Swarabheda</i> (Hoarseness of voice), <i>Vakagraha</i> (Aphasia)	+	-	+	+
30.	<i>Gadagadaty</i> (Dysarthria)	+	-	+	+
31.	<i>Kanharoga</i> (Throat Disease)	+	-	+	+
32.	<i>Swarakshaya</i>	-	-	+	+
33.	<i>Nidranasha</i>	+	-	+	+
34.	<i>Krichaavabodha</i> (Difficulty in awake)	-	+	+	+

Table No. 8: Contraindications of *Nasya Karma*.

Sr. No	Nasya Ayogya	Charak (Ch.Si2/20)	Sushruta (Ch40/47)	Ah. Su. 20/11-13	Sharangdhara	B.P
1.	<i>Ajirna</i> (Indigestion)	+	+		+	+
2.	<i>Bhuktabhakta</i> (After Meals)	+	+	+	+	+
3.	<i>Snehapita</i>	+	+	+	+	+
4.	<i>Madyapita</i> (After intake of Alcohol)	+	+	+		
5.	<i>Toyapita</i> (After intake of water)	+	+	+	+	+
6.	<i>Snehadi Patukama</i> (client who has taken sneha)	+		+	-	-
7.	<i>Snatashira</i> (Post bath), <i>Snatukama</i> (who have to bath)	+	+	+	-	-
8.	<i>Kshudhrta</i> (Hungry patient)	+	-	-	-	-
9.	<i>Trishnartha</i> (thirsty)	+	+	-	+	+
10.	<i>Shramarha</i> (Exerted Patient)	+	-	-	-	-
11.	<i>Murchita</i> (Unconscious)	+	-	-	-	-
12.	<i>Matta</i>	+	-	-	-	-
13.	<i>Shastradandahata</i> (injured by weapon)	+	-	-	-	-
14.	<i>Vyavyaklanta</i> (Exerted by Coitus)	+	-	-	-	-

15.	Vyamaklanta (exerted due to gym)	+	-	-	-	-
16.	Panaklanta (exerted due to thirst)	+	-	-	-	-
17.	Navajwara	+	-	-	-	-
18.	Shokabhitapta	+	+	-	+	-
19.	Vikrikta	+	-	+	-	-
20.	Amuvasita	+	+	+	+	+
21.	Garbhini	+	+	-	+	+
22.	Anruto(Unseasonal)	+	+	+	+	+
23.	Navapratishaya	+	+	+	+	+
24.	Durdina	+	+	+	+	+
25.	Apatarpita	-	+	-	-	-
26.	Pitadrava	-	+	-	-	-
27.	Gararta	-	+	+	+	+
28.	Krodha	-	+	-	+	+
29.	Bala	-	+	-	+	+
30.	Vrudha	-	+	-	+	+
31.	Vegavrodha	-	+	+	+	+
32.	Anartava	-	+	+	-	-
33.	Raktavistravita	-	-	+	-	-
34.	Sutika	-	-	+	-	-
35.	Shavasapidita	-	-	+	-	-
36.	Kasapidita	-	-	+	-	-
37.	Pita-aasava	-	-	-	-	+

Administration of Nasya

The procedure of giving *Nasya* therapy may be classified into the following three headings.

1. *Purvakarma* (Pre-measures)
2. *Pradhanakarma* (*Nasya* therapy)
3. *Paschatkarma* (Post measures)

1) *Purvakarma*

Before giving *Nasya*, prior arrangement of the material and equipments should be done. There should be a special room "*Nasya Bhavana*" free from atmospheric effects like direct blow of air and dust, etc. and lighted appropriately. In it the following articles should be collected.

- (i) *Nasya Asana* - (a) A chair for sitting purpose. (b) A cot for lying purpose.
- (ii) *Nasya Aushadhi* – Drugs required for induction and management of *Shirovirechana* should be collected in the form of *Kalka*, *Churna*, *Kwatha*, *Kshira*, *Udaka*, *Sneha*, *Asava*, *Dhuma* etc. in sufficient quantity.
- (iii) *Nasya Yantra* - For *Snehana*, *Avapida*, *Marsha* and *Pratimarsha Nasya*, there should be a dropper or *Pichu*. For *Pradhmana Nasya Shadangula Nadi* and specific *Dhumayantra* for *Dhum Nasya* are required.

Besides this one needs efficient assistant, dressing material, spitting pots, bowl, napkins and towels also.

• **Selection of the patient:** The patient should be selected according to the indications and contraindications of *Nasya* described in classics.

• **Preparation of patient:** According to *Sushruta's* description following

1. Regimens are given to the patient to prepare him for *Nasya Karma*.
2. Patient should have passed his natural urges like urine & stool.
3. Should have completed his routine activities like tooth brushing, bath, etc.
4. Light breakfast 1 hr prior to *Nasya karma* is advised.
5. Now the patient is ready for *Nasya karma*. He should lie down on *Nasya* table. Before *Nasya*, *Mridu*
6. *Abhyanga* (massage) should be done on scalp, forehead, face and neck for 3 to 5 minutes by medicated oil like *Bala Taila*, *Panchaguna Taila* etc.
7. *Snehapana* should not be given immediately before *Nasyakarma*.
8. *Swedana* should not be given to the head. *Mridu Swedana* may be given for elimination of *Doshas* and liquification of *Doshas*. *Tapa sweda* may be given on *Shira*, *Mukha*, *Nasa*, *Manya*, *Griva* and *Kantha* region. Cloth dipped in hot water may be useful for *Mridu Sweda*. After *Swedana* smooth massage should be applied on regions of *Gala*, *Kapola* and *Lalata*.

2) *Pradhana Karma*

According to *Charaka*, *Vagbhat* and *Sushrut*, the following procedure should be adopted for performing the *Nasya Karma*.

1. Patient should lie down in supine position with ease on *Nasya* table.
2. *Shira* (head) should be "*Pralambita*" (lowered i.e. hanging down) and feet are slightly raised.
3. Head should not be excessively flexed or extended.

4. If the head is not lowered, the *Nasal* medication may not reach to the desired distinction and if it is lowered too much, there may be the danger of getting the medication to be lodged in brain.
5. After covering the eyes with clean cotton cloth, the physician should raise the tip of the patient's nose with his left thumb and with the right hand the luke warm medicine (*Sukhoshna* drug) should be dropped in both the nostrils alternately in proper way.
6. The drug should be neither less nor more in the dose i.e. it should be in the proper quantity.
7. It should also be neither very hot nor very cold. i.e. it should be luke warm.
8. The patient should remain relaxed while taking *Nasya*. He should avoid speech, anger, sneezing, laughing and head shaking during *Nasya Karma*.

3) Paschat Karma

According to *Charaka*, *Ashtanga Hridaya* and *Sushruta*, following regimen should be followed.

After administration of medication through *Nasal* passage patient should lie supine (*Uttana*) for about 2 minute time interval & ask him to count numbers upto 100. After an administration of *Nasya* feets, shoulders, palms and ears should be massaged. The head, cheek and neck should be again subjected to sudation.

1. The patient should avoid swallowing of *Nasya* *Aaushadhi*.
2. The oil that has been dropped in the nose may be repeatedly drained out together with the morbid *Doshas*, especially mucus; should be eliminated by the patient by sneezing slowly.
3. Care should be taken that no portion of the medicated oil is left behind.
4. Patient should spit out the excessive medicines which have come into the oropharynx.
5. Medicated *Dhumapana* and *Gandusha* are advocated to expel out the residue mucus lodged in *Kantha* (gullet) and *Shringataka*.
6. Patient should stay at windless place. Light meal (*Laghu Aahara*) and luke warm water (*Sukhoshna Jala*) is allowed.
7. Patient should avoid dust, smoke, sunshine, alcohol, hot bath, riding, anger, excess fat and liquid diet.

Importance of Post Nasya Massage

1. A comfortable light massage on the frontal, temporal, maxillary, mastoid & on *Manya* regions may help to subsides the irritation of somatic constriction due to heat stimulation.
2. It may also help in removing the slush created in these regions.
3. However, interesting here is regarding *Manya* which is a *Marma* existing in neck on either side of the trachea which likely correspond to the carotid sinuses of the neck.
4. Pressure applied on the baroreceptors may bring the dearranged cerebral arterial pressure to normalcy (Hejmadi S. 1985). Because these receptors lying on bed of bifurcation of common carotid artery have a

buffering action on the cerebral arterial pressure (Best & Taylor 1958).

Mode of Action of Nasya

A clear description regarding the mode of action of *Nasya Karma* is not available in Ayurvedic classics. *Acharya Charaka* has described that *Nasa* is the only gateway to *Shirah*. (Ch. Si. 9/88). So, the medicine administered through *Nasa* can easily spread to *Shirah* and get absorbed.

Acharya Vagbhatta has given some more details about the mode of action (As.S.Su.29/2).^[12] It is explained that *Nasa* being gate way to *Shirah*, the drug administered through nostrils reaches *Shringataka*, a *Siramarma* by *Nasa Srota* and spreads in the *Murdha* (Brain), taking routes of *Netra* (Eyes), *Shrotra* (Ears), *Kantha* (Throat) and stretches the morbid *Doshas* from *Urdhwajatru* and expels them from *Uttamanga*.

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